

When 'Holi Speaks'

Holi comes splashing colours in life.
Adding colours teaches us lessons of life.
Be like me!
Holi appeals with great glee.
Though dead but full of life.
Though silent but pregnant with voice.

For me no friend and enemy.
No black and white.
Every human is bright.
Everyone has equal share in my delight

No touchable and untouchable.
No rich and poor.
No fair and unfair.
In my eyes all are fair.

No man and a woman.
In my colours no discrimination.
No ugly and fair.
In my colours every colour is fair.

I am neither a teacher nor a philosopher.
I am neither a saint nor a sage.
But help you in many ways
To come out of the narrow cage.

In life distressed,
I make you feel a little relaxed.
Looking at my colours' beauty,
For a moment you forget your daily anxiety.

This much little I can do.
And this much little I can teach you.
After all it's up to you
To take me with or not with you.

I am neither a mentor nor a guide.
Not clever and wise like you.
I feel something for you.
So, I think for you.

If possible just once in your life,
Play the role of mine.
Then see the magic
Life will be beautiful and full of smiles.

Sorry if I expect a lot.
It's my day today.
You can give me this much.
I think it's not a lot today.

About the poet: Prof. Dr. Balasaheb Ishwar Wakde has been working as an assistant Professor of English in MIT School of Computing, MIT ADT University, Pune, Maharashtra. He has authored several books and published many research papers and poems in various national and international journals.